

1. Review title

Systemic glucocorticoids as adjunctive therapy in severe community-acquired pneumonia in adults: a systematic review

2. Review question

In adult patients with severe community-acquired pneumonia, does adjunctive treatment with systemic glucocorticoids, compared with standard antibiotic therapy alone, improve clinical outcomes and reduce mortality?

3. Condition or domain being studied

Severe community-acquired pneumonia (CAP) is associated with high morbidity and mortality, particularly among patients requiring intensive care. Although prompt antibiotic therapy is the cornerstone of treatment, as recommended by the Infectious Diseases Society of America and the American Thoracic Society, mortality rates remain substantial. This suggests that pathogen eradication alone may be insufficient to prevent adverse outcomes.

In severe CAP, an exaggerated systemic inflammatory response plays a central role in respiratory failure, septic shock, and organ dysfunction. Systemic glucocorticoids have been proposed as adjunctive therapy due to their anti-inflammatory effects, with the potential to reduce inflammation-related complications and improve clinical outcomes. However, existing studies show heterogeneous results regarding mortality reduction and safety, particularly concerning hyperglycemia and secondary infections. Differences in corticosteroid type, dosage, and patient severity further contribute to uncertainty. Therefore, a systematic review focused exclusively on severe CAP is warranted to critically evaluate the balance between benefits and risks of adjunctive systemic glucocorticoids compared to standard antibiotic therapy alone. This review aims to clarify current evidence and support evidence-based management of severe CAP.

4. Participants / Population

- Adults (≥ 18 years) with Community-acquired Pneumonia admitted on hospital.

5. Intervention(s), exposure(s)

Systemic glucocorticoid therapy, regardless of type, dose, or duration.

6. Comparator(s) / control

Placebo, standard care, or no glucocorticoid therapy.

7. Study types to be included

The review of clinical effectiveness will include only RCTs

8. Main outcome(s)

Primary outcome: All cause mortality (in hospital or 30 day mortality).

9. Additional outcome(s)

Secondary outcomes will include clinically relevant measures of disease progression, healthcare utilization, and safety. These will comprise length of hospital stay, length of intensive care unit (ICU) stay, need for mechanical ventilation, duration of mechanical ventilation, time to clinical stability, and treatment failure as defined by individual studies. Safety outcomes will include adverse events related to systemic glucocorticoid use, particularly hyperglycemia requiring treatment, secondary infections, gastrointestinal bleeding, and other reported corticosteroid-related complications.

10. Search strategy

We will search MEDLINE (via PubMed), Embase, Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials (CENTRAL), and Web of Science from inception to the date of search. No language restrictions will be applied. Reference lists of included studies will be manually screened.

11. Data extraction

Two independent reviewers will screen titles and abstracts, assess full texts for eligibility, and extract data using a standardized form. Disagreements will be resolved by consensus or by a third reviewer.

12. Risk of bias assessment

Risk of bias will be assessed using the Cochrane Risk of Bias 2.0 tool.

13. Strategy for data synthesis

If appropriate, a meta-analysis will be conducted using a random-effects model. Heterogeneity will be assessed using the I^2 statistic. Subgroup and sensitivity analyses will be performed when applicable.

14. Analysis of subgroups

- Dose of glucocorticoid
- Duration of therapy
- Severity of disease

15. Assessment of reporting bias

Publication bias will be assessed using funnel plots and Egger's test when at least 10 studies are included.

16. Certainty of evidence

The certainty of evidence will be evaluated using the GRADE approach.

17. Review team details

Amanda Almeida Cavalcanti de Melo
Universidade Católica de Pernambuco, Pernambuco/Brasil
amandaalmeidaac9@gmail.com

Jadeany Sabrine Bertoudo machado Valença
Universidade de Pernambuco, Pernambuco/Brasil

Laura Margarida Veiga Pereira
Universidade de Pernambuco, Pernambuco/Brasil

Ruan Ng Portela
Universidade de Pernambuco, Pernambuco/Brasil

Júlio Tavares dos Santos Cruz
Faculdade Pernambucana de Saúde, Pernambuco/Brasil

Ruan Matheus Alves da Silva
Universidade Católica de Pernambuco, Pernambuco/Brasil

Lissa Okazaki
Universidade de Pernambuco, Pernambuco/Brasil

This review has no external funding.